

Thesis for the Degree of Master of Science in Construction Management

**“Analysis of the Aggregate Strength Variation at Selected
Section of Biring River Basin”**

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(2019-1-06-0023)

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Urlabari -3, Morang

November, 2021

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**“Analysis of the Aggregate Strength Variation at Selected
Section of Biring River Basin”**

Supervised by

Er. Binod Aryal, Ph.D.

A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirement for the
Degree of Master of Science in Construction Management

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DECLARATION

I Hereby declare that this study entitled " **Analysis of the Aggregate Strength Variation at Selected Section of Biring River Basin** " was based on my original research work. Related works on the topic , by other researcher, have been duly acknowledged. I owe all the liabilities relating to accuracy and authenticity of the data or any information include hereunder.

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Recommendation

This is to certify that this thesis entitled “**Analysis of the Aggregate Strength Variation at Selected Section of Biring River Basin**” prepared and submitted by **Niraj Adhikari**, in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the degree of Master of Science (M.Sc.) in Construction Management Engineering awarded by Pokhara University, has been completed under my/our supervision. I/we recommend the same for acceptance by Pokhara University.

Signature

Name of the Supervisor: Er. Binod Aryal, Ph.D.

Organization: Madan Bhandari Technological University Development Board

Date: November, 2021

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Finally, I would like to thanks to all, who have done directly and indirectly assists to me for this effort. I dedicate this works to my Family.

Signature:

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Abstract

There is high demand of aggregates material in the construction industry of Nepal. Till date, river borne aggregate material fulfills major part of the demand. Among various river, Biring river is one of the major river in Province 1. The objective of this research was to analysis of Aggregate strength variation at selected section of Biring river basin. The selected section of Biring river is about 20 Km of Arjundhara Municipality. For research purpose, representative samples from selected six sites along the river were collected on the basis of accessibility and deposition. Lab Test for Physical properties (Fineness Modulus, Water Absorption and Specific Gravity) and mechanical properties (Los Angles Abrasion, Aggregate Impact Value and Aggregate Crushing value were conducted on those sample to evaluate their quality for the construction works. Also 18 cubes (3 each from 6 selected site) were casted to evaluate their compressive strength variation. A linear relationship between the ACV, AIV and LAA value with longitudinal variation of river was established. Also the economic analysis of revenue collected by selling the aggregate of Biring River was done .

After conducting the lab test of physical properties of aggregate, Fineness Modulus, Water Absorption and Specific Gravity were found in the range of (7.16-7.49)%, (0.72-1.15)% and (2.616-2.712) %. A linear equation for the longitudinal variation in the LAA, AIV and ACV value was established. For a longitudinal variation equation for LAA value $y = -0.352x + 37.41$ ACV value an equation $y = -0.212x + 29.88$ and AIV value an equation $y = -0.0189x + 27.15$ where $y =$ Value of LAA, AIV and ACV value and $x =$ distance in km from upstream origin point. The average compressive strength for 7 and 28 days of all cubes were found to be within standard required. The economic contribution of revenue collected by selling the river bed materials as aggregate of Biring river on the total internal revenue of Arjundhara Municipality was found to be significant that is about 30.86%.

So, after conducting Lab test for physical and mechanical properties, it was concluded that the aggregate material becomes more suitable in their hardness, toughness and strength on moving from upstream towards the downstream along the Biring river. The lower portion of river was judged to have relatively quality of aggregates.

Keywords: Cement concrete, aggregate sources, properties of aggregates, compressive strength of concrete, Internal revenue, economic contribution.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACI	American Concrete institute
BWAS	Bureau of Indian standard
CA	Coarse Aggregate
FA	Fine Aggregate
gm	Gram
WAS	Indian Standard
Kg	Kilogram
LAA	Los Angeles Abrasion
AIV	Aggregate Impact Value
ACV	Aggregate Crushing Strength
m	Meter
M20	20 N/mm ² at 28 days of concrete
mm	Millimeter
Mpa	Mega Pascal
N	Newton
NS	Nepal Standard
W/C	Water Cement ratio
sg	Specific Gravity

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Cement concrete is a mixture of cement, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate and water in a certain prescribed proportion (Murali, 2019). It is the one of the most frequent used materials. Many types of concrete are available, determined by the formulations of binders and the types of aggregate used to suit the application for the material. concrete is the most commonly used construction material in the world (S. & Pravesh, 2019), the quality of the concrete used is an important factor in construction, which is determined primarily by its compressive strength (Muhammad, Uneb, Mohammed, Omar S., & Imran, 2020). These variables determine strength, density, as well as chemical and thermal resistance of the finished product. The size distribution of the aggregate determines how much binder is required. Aggregate with a very even size distribution has the biggest gaps whereas adding aggregate with smaller particles tends to fill these gaps. The binder must fill the gaps between the aggregate as well as paste the surfaces of the aggregate together, and is typically the most expensive component. Thus, variation in sizes of the aggregate reduces the cost of concrete. So the size and quality directly affect the economy and strength of the concrete.

Aggregates are the most important constituents in concrete. They give body to the concrete, reduce shrinkage and effect economy. Natural aggregates are inert granular materials such as sand, gravel stone or crushed stone that are used with a binding medium i.e. water, bitumen, portland cement, lime, etc. to form compound materials i.e. asphalt concrete and portland cement concrete.

Almost all the natural aggregate materials originate from igneous, sedimentary and metamorphic rocks. The concrete making properties of natural aggregates are influenced to some extent on the basis of geological formation of the parent rock together with the subsequent processes of weathering and alteration. Due to weathering, alteration, attrition, corrosion and hydraulic action the rock get break into smaller pieces and thus breakable pieces are transported by the river and deposited in plain area. Therefore river is a major source of natural aggregates. Water resources not only produced different forms of energy but also carry the large sediments from the lesser and Sub- Himalayans to Terai region. The river sediments are chiefly gravel with few sand and mud. Gravel (coarse aggregates greater than 4.75 mm) can be easily collected from the river area after deposition during

each flood season. Hence, the river is perennial source of coarse aggregates. The use of coarse aggregate which are extracted from the river as construction material has been extensive because of high demand in construction works.

Among them, Biring River is stream, one of the important River of Jhapa District flowing in a general direction towards south West. A Stream is a body of running water moving to a lower level in a channel on land. It is classified as class H – (Hydrographic) and Its coordinates are 26°34'60" N and 87°54'0" E in DMS (Degrees Minutes Seconds) or 26.5833 and 87.9 (in decimal degrees). Its UTM position is WK84 and its Joint Operation Graphics reference is NG45-07. The estimate terrain elevation of Biring River above sea level is 68 metres. The Biring River is a Churia River which is originating from Siwalik and churia Hills and It is considered as one of the most vulnerable Churia river in Jhapa.

Large amount of construction materials is required For Jhapa district in the form of fine and coarse aggregates for development of infrastructure which can be extracted from the deposition of Biring River. The major infrastructure such as irrigation, roads, urban development, water supply scheme, hydropower that can be develop with in the Biring basin also demands huge amount of construction materials whose quality is of great concern.

Due to aggradation and degradation nature of river large amount of materials is transported from the upper zone to lower zone. The flowing materials deposited by the river is of high strength due to wear and tear and impact provided by the water force. Such materials are free of dust and easy on extractions. From the economic point of view such river bed materials are relatively cheap compared to crushed ones. So to know the different physical and mechanical properties of such aggregates a study of such materials is very important.

1.2 Statement of Problem

The Himalaya is a source of material transported downstream by river surges and deposited in their piedmont. Consequently, the immediate Himalayan piedmont is an area where river bed sediments are intensively extracted. Thus sediments materials are the major source of construction materials in Nepal for various infrastructure development works.

A study should be carried out to determine the quality of materials deposited at various piedmont. Though the materials are of the same source, they might possess different characteristics due to repetitive wear and tear. Due to high current of water many impacts

are faced by the river bed materials. As we go downstream part of the river the properties of aggregates may vary for same size of particles. To study those properties of aggregates is essential.

This study also carried out to determine the economic contribution of the revenue collected by selling the river bed material as aggregates of Biring river Basin based on Environment consequences analysis based on the information collected from Arjunthara Municipality.

1.3 Reasearch Questions

This Research work will give the answer of following questions.

1. How is the physical and mechanical characteristics of aggregates at different locations of Biring River?
2. What is the suitability of the aggregates collected from selected section of Biring river basin for Road construction works as per norms and specification of DOR?
3. what is contribution of revenue collected by selling aggregates of Biring river basin in the total internal revenue of Arjunthara Municipality?

1.4 Research Objectives

The overall objective of research is to analysis aggregate strength variation at selected section of Biring river basin.

The specific objective of study are:

1. To determine the physical (Fineness Modulus, Specific gravity and water absorption) and mechanical characteristics (Los Angeles abrasion, Aggregate impact value and Aggregate crushing value) of aggregates at selected section of Biring river basin and their linear relationship with longitudinal variation of river.
2. To assure the suitability of aggregates based on compressive strength assesment of specimens prepared from selected section of Biring river basin.
3. To determine the contribution of revenue collected by selling Aggregates of Biring river basin in the total internal source of Income of Arjunthara Municipality.

1.5 Significance of the Study

In Construction industry the demand of aggregates for road and concrete works is increasing day by day. Aggregate occupies most of the volume of the concrete and road works. Aggregates are generally thought of as inert structural filler within a concrete mix. But a closer look reveals the major role and influence aggregate plays in the properties of both fresh and hardened concrete. Changes in gradation, maximum size, unit weight, and moisture content can all alter the character and performance of concrete mix. Aggregate is also used for base and sub-base courses for both flexible and rigid pavements. Different types of loads are carried by the aggregates so there should be a thorough study on the properties of aggregates that are to be used in road construction. Road aggregates should have adequate strength, hardness, toughness, shape, adhesion with bitumen, durability and free from deleterious materials. Different types of tests can be carried to find out those properties. Crushing, abrasion, impact, soundness, specific gravity and water absorption, shape and bitumen adhesion etc are some of the test to be carried out to find out the desirable properties of the road aggregates. From this study physical and mechanical properties of the aggregates available along the Biring River can be known. This study will be significant for local authorities and othe all other construction stakeholders for assuring the quality of the aggregates of Biring river at different section for Road construction project and othe construction works.

1.6 Scope and Limitation of Study

1.6.1 Scope

The analysis of coarse aggregate form different section of Biring River will be performed with specific gravity test, water absorption test, Sieve analysis, impact value test, abrasion value test of coarse aggregate, which is most essential in construction field. Also 18 cubes (3 each from 6 different source) are prepared from aggregate collected to calculate Compressive strength of concrete (M20 grade) by keeping Other factors such as properties of cement, water/cement ratio, use of chemical and admixtures etc unchanged for all sample specimens. The significance of economic contibution of revenue collected as aggregates of Biring river are analysed by information collected from Arjundhara Municipality.

1.6.2 Limitation

- There are many variables that control the strength of concrete. Among them cement content and its properties, properties of fine aggregates, water content and its property, type of admixture and its dosage, degree and method of compaction and duration of curing which directly affects the strength of concrete. These factors are not considered.
- Among the total length of Biring river only Arjundhara Section (Approx 20 KM) is considered since the upper slope are very steep and rare in deposition. The sampling will be done from outside the water body from the deposited stock.
- The chemical properties of the aggregate are not considered for the research study.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

Concrete is one of the oldest and most common construction materials in the world, mainly due to its low cost, availability, its long durability, and ability to sustain extreme weather environments (Tantawi, 2015a). Although aggregate is considered inert filler, it is a necessary component that defines the concrete's thermal and elastic properties and dimensional stability. Aggregates have different physical, chemical, mechanical and thermal properties (Zega et al., 2010). The compressive aggregate strength is an important factor in the selection of aggregate. The compressive strength of concrete depends on the water to cement ratio, degree of compaction, ratio of cement to aggregate, bond between mortar and aggregate, and grading, shape, strength and size of the aggregate (Abdullahi, 2012). Physical and mineralogical properties of aggregate must be known before mixing concrete to obtain a desirable mixture. These properties include shape and texture, size gradation, moisture content, specific gravity, reactivity, soundness and bulk unit weight. These properties along with the water/cementitious material ratio determine the strength, workability, and durability of concrete. Aggregates strongly influence concrete's freshly mixed and hardened properties, mixture proportions, and economy. Consequently, selection of aggregates is an important process. Although some variation in aggregate properties is expected, characteristics that are considered include:

- i. grading
- ii. durability
- iii. particle shape and surface texture
- iv. abrasion and skid resistance
- v. unit weights and voids
- vi. absorption and surface moisture

2.2 Properties of Aggregate

2.2.1 Physical Properties

i) Grading

Grading of the aggregate represents the particle size distribution of the aggregate particles in the aggregate mass and influence the properties of the concrete or other structure. It is determined by sieve analysis using the set of standard sieves and presented in the particle

size distribution curve. well graded material was generally suitable for concreting and other purposes due to the smaller particles fill the voids between the larger particles and help to become dense and economies the quantity of cement used (Ajagbe & Tijani, 2018). Gap grading was when a certain size of particles was not present in the mass. Uniformly grading was when the same range of material were present in the gravel mass.

ii) Shape

The shape of the aggregate depends upon the source of the aggregate. The shape may be rounded, irregular, angular, flaky elongated etc. Different index such as flakiness index, elongation index, angularity number etc were developed to define the shape of aggregates.

iii) Size

Aggregate was designated with the nominal size. It was determined by the sieve analysis and each nominal sized aggregate should fit in the corresponding grading limits.

iv) Texture

Surface texture depends upon the hardness, grain size and pore characteristics of parent rock. Visual estimation of roughness was quite reliable. Texture may glossy, smooth, granular, rough, crystalline, honey combed etc.

v) Specific Gravity

Specific gravity of aggregate can be determined by using pycnometer method. It is the ratio of weight of aggregate of certain volume to that of water of same volume.

vi) Bulk density

It is the ratio of the weight of the sample to its respective volume.

vii) Water Absorption

Absorption test can be carried out to determine the water absorption of the aggregate. It was the amount of water absorbed by the sample of the aggregate.

viii) Bulking of Aggregate

It was noticeable in case of fine aggregate only. it was the process of rise in the volume of the aggregate due to moisture content before reaching to the submerged condition.

2.2.2 Mechanical Properties of Aggregate

i) Crushing Strength

It was the resistance of the aggregate against crushing under gradually applied load. It was determined by using standard crushing test in the laboratory.

ii) Hardness

It was the resistance of aggregate against the wearing. It can be determined by using the Los Angeles Abrasion.

iii) Toughness

It was the resistance of aggregate against impact. It can be determined by aggregate Impact value in the laboratory.

iv) Bond strength

It was the resistance developed to shear the aggregate particles from the hardened cement paste was called bond strength of aggregate.

2.2.3 Thermal Properties of Aggregate

i) Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

It was the material property that was indicative of the extent to which a material expands upon heating.

ii) Specific Heat:

The specific heat was the amount of heat per unit mass required to raise the temperature by one degree Celsius.

iii) Thermal Conductivity

It was the ability of aggregate to conduct heat through it.

2.2.4 Chemical Properties of Aggregate

Aggregate is normally taken as the inert material but in some cases some aggregate may contain reactive silica which reacts with alkalies (sodium/potassium oxide) present in cement called alkali aggregate reaction.

2.3 Requirements for Different Types of Road Construction

In this section, the different physical properties requirements that should be fulfilled by the aggregate in different forms such as Sub base, Base and wearing course will be mentioned

and all the data will be followed from the yellow book named as " Standard specification for Road and Bridge works" prepared and used by " **Ministry of Physical Infrastructure and Transport**". Crusher Run material properties will not be mentioned.

Table 2.1 Physical Requirements (Granular Sub Base)

Physical Properties	Test Method	Requirement for class I and II	Requirement for class III, IV and maintenance work
Aggregate Impact value (AIV)	WAS 2386-4 or 5640	Maximum 40	Maximum 45
Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV)	WAS: 2384-4 or WAS: 5640**	Maximum 40	Maximum 45

Source: DOR Specification 2073

Table 2.2 Physical Requirements (Water Bound Macadam For Sub Base / Base Course)

Properties	Requirements (Base)	Requirement (Sub Base)	Test Method
Loss Angeles Abrasion Value (LAA)	40 Max	45 Max	WAS: 2386-4
Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV)	30 Max	40 Max	WAS: 2384-4 or WAS: 5640**
Aggregate Impact Value (AIV)	30 Max	40 Max	WAS: 2384-4 or WAS: 5640**

Source: DOR Specification 2073

Note

- i) ** Aggregate which get softened in presence of water shall be tested for Impact value under wet condition as per WAS : 5640
- ii) *** The requirement of flakiness and elongation index shall be enforced only in case of crushed broken stone and crushed slag.

Table 2.3 Physical Requirements (Wet Mixed Macadam Sub Base and Base Course)

Physical Properties	Test Method	Requirement for class I and II (Max %)		Requirement for class III and IV (Max %)	
		Base (B1)	Sub Base (B2)	Base (S1)	Sub Base (S2)
Los Angeles Abrasion Value	WAS: 2386-4	40	45		

(LAA)					
Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV)	WAS: 5640	30	35**	40**	45**
Aggregate Impact Value (AIV)	WAS: 5640	30	35**	40**	45**

Source: DOR Specification 2073

Note

*B1,B2, S1 and S2 are the classes of Materials

** In case of low graded aggregates, wet aggregate Impact Value (test method WAS: 5640) should not exceed given range and thickness of the pavement layer should be at least 15 cm.

Table 2.4 Physical Requirements (Surface Dressing an Dense Bituminous Macadam Road)

Properties	Specification/Requirement	Test method
Los Angeles Abrasion Value (LAA)	Max 35%	WAS: 2386 (Part -4)
Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV)	Max 27%	WAS: 2386 (Part -4)
Aggregate Impact Value (AIV)	Max 27%	WAS: 2386 (Part -4)

Source: DOR Specification 2073

Table 2.5 Physical Requirements (Otta Seal, Penetration Macadam and Bituminous Macadam)

Property	Test	Specification	Method of Test
Strength	Los Angeles Abrasion Value (LAA)	Max 40%	WAS: 2386 (Part iv)
Strength	Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV)	Max 30%	WAS: 2386 (Part iv)
Strength	Aggregate Impact Value (AIV)	Max 30%	WAS: 2386 (Part iv)

Source: DOR Specification 2073

Table 2.6 Physical Requirements (Asphalt Concrete or Bituminous Concrete)

Property	Test	Specification	Method of Test
Strength	Los Angeles Abrasion Value (LAA)	Max 30%	WAS: 2386 (Part iv)
Strength	Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV)	Max 24%	WAS: 2386 (Part iv)
Strength	Aggregate Impact Value (AIV)	Max 24%	WAS: 2386 (Part iv)

Source: DOR Specification 2073

2.4 Empirical Review

Study conducted by (Madai & Khadka, 2019) to find the suitability of aggregates of Kavre and Sindhuli district quarries for road construction materials using the standard test procedure, they found that the aggregates materials from all three quarries (Challal Ganesh- Kavre; Aapghari- Ghampyakhola; Bhyakurkhola) taken in that study was met the standard required to use the materials for different layer of flexible pavement.

Study done by (Maharjan & Tamrakar, 2008) in Rapti River to evaluate the quality of gravel for concrete and road aggregates to know its suitability, the different properties such as petrographic, physical, mechanical and chemical properties were analysed and it was found that the majority of sample had rounded, surface texture was rough to smooth, the water absorption value from 0.69 to 1.12%, dry density ranged from 2460 to 2680 kg/m³, aggregates impact values of samples ranges from 14.2 to 16.1% and magnesium sulphate values ranged from 4.46 to 7.19% . All the tested results were complied with the exiting Nepal Standard, British Standard and American Standard and it showed that the samples were suitable for road aggregates and for concrete also.

A study done by (Mishra et al., 2020) in Gautam Buddha Airport to assess the factors which affect quality and the standard conformance of cement and coarse aggregates used at the construction site by using the key informant interview, questionnaires survey along with laboratory test of coarse aggregates and cement, they found that the average Compressive strength of concrete cube of 3 days, 7 days and 28days is 18.8N/mm²(>16N/mm²), 27.20N/mm²(>22N/mm²) and 39.40N/mm²(>33N/mm²) respectively. The average initial setting Time and final setting time of cement is 180 min(>45min) and 351 min(<600min) respectively and average soundness of cement is 2.7mm(<10mm). The test for aggregate, they found that average Los Angeles Abrasion value of aggregate was 32.8%(<40%), average crushing value of aggregate was 19.88%(<25%), Flakiness index of aggregate found that 19.85%(<25%) and the gradation of aggregate was found that within specification and major factors affecting quality was the unavailability of competent staff, Low quality drawing and specification and Poor-quality procedure.

The Romans are well known for their extensive use of concrete more than two millennia ago, yet experience and knowledge of cement materials is still developing and expanding. Scientific research into cement and concrete technology surged dramatically from the beginning of the 20th century with the growing use of steel-reinforced concrete, but even

today, almost 180 years after the first patent for Portland cement, many gaps in our understanding remain. Concrete has been one of the most widely used building materials over the past 100 years. It has made possible numerous complex structures, ranging from bridges, monuments and buildings, to civil engineering works.

The earliest use of concrete dates back to before 5600 BC: a 250-mm floor slab from this period, which was made using a red lime, sand and gravel mix, has been discovered on the banks of the Danube in Yugoslavia. In Egypt, murals dating from 1950 BC show various stages of the process of making concrete (Stanley 1980). The first concrete used was mass or plain concrete, which exploited its great strength in compression. This was produced using limestone, which was burnt to form lime or natural cement. To make concrete that would set and harden, the lime had to have sufficiently high hydraulic properties; that is, the concrete had to be able to set in water or when exposed to only a small amount of air.

The Investigation paper “Effect of coarse aggregate quality on the mechanical properties of high strength Concrete” (H Beshr, A.A Almusallam, M Maslehuddin 2003) results of a study conducted to evaluate the effect of four types of coarse aggregates, namely calcareous, dolomitic, quartzitic limestone, and steel slag, on the compressive and tensile strength, and elastic modulus of high strength concrete. The highest and lowest compressive strength was obtained in the concrete specimens prepared with steel slag and calcareous limestone aggregates, respectively. Similarly, the split tensile strength of steel slag aggregate concrete was the highest, followed by that of dolomitic and quartzitic limestone aggregate concretes. The lowest split tensile strength was noted in the calcareous limestone aggregate concrete. The type of coarse aggregate also influences the modulus of elasticity of concrete.

The paper “The Effect of Maximum Coarse Aggregate Size on the Compressive Strength of Concrete Produced in Ghana” (Anthony W 2015) concluded that the compressive strength of concrete made with 10 mm maximum aggregate size is higher than that of 14mm and 20mm sizes. However, the slump values of concrete made with 20mm sizes of gneisses is higher than that of 10mm and 14mm size gneisses at the same water/cement ratio. Consequently the optimum maximum coarse aggregate size for the best compressive strength of 28 day concrete was found to be 8mm for water/cement ratio of 0.63. The optimum ratio of the maximum size of fine aggregate to the maximum size of coarse aggregate for the highest compressive strength is 0.18 for the water/cement ratio selected. This shows that the greater the heterogeneity the lower the compressive strength of concrete.

The paper “Effect of coarse aggregate type on mechanical properties of high-performance concrete” (Ke-Ru Wu, Bing Chen, Wu Yao, Dong Zhang 1997) concluded that the impact of the type of coarse aggregate on the strength of concrete is more significant in high-strength concrete. In high-strength concretes in the present study, about 10-20% higher compressive and splitting tensile strengths are obtained with crushed quartzite compared to marble aggregate. The results of fracture energy show that besides the fracture mechanical properties of the aggregates, the type of coarse aggregates has significant effects on the fracture energy. It is suggested that the high-strength concrete with lower brittleness can be made by selecting high-strength aggregate with low brittleness.

Similarly, a study done by (Nayaju & Tamrakar, 2019) to evaluate the fine aggregates from Budhi Gandaki- Narayani River which is rich in carrying natural fine aggregates from Higher and Lesser Himalayas region, the fine aggregates gradation curve showed that aggregates were varied from uniform to well graded, the deleterious materials excluding organic matter range from 0.3%-1.5% and presence of organic matter range from 0.57% - 1.11%. They wrote the trend showed that the presence of inorganic deleterious material and presence of organic matter is increasing towards southern segments of the river. Study showed that the bulk density of aggregate is below 2gm/cc, specific gravity ranges between 1.49 to 1.79, fineness modulus range from 1.36 to 3.50 and the value of water absorption ranges between 0.48 to 2.87%.

2.5 Research Gap

Few researches have been done in Nepal to ensure the effect of aggregate sources on compressive strength of concrete. In the research paper published by (Prajapati & Karanjit, 2019), researchers show the coarse aggregate source had significant variation in the compressive strength of various grade of nominal concrete mix. They tested concrete cube of five different coarse aggregates sources from where aggregates were quarried for Kathmandu valley. Among few researches done in this research area, the research done in this research topic cannot cover the Jhapa district and most of the researches are oriented in Kathmandu valley and other major cities of Nepal. To fulfil the gap in research between developed cities with developing cities this research will show the effect of aggregate sources on physical and mechanical properties and compressive strength of concrete of Biringriverbasin.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Area

Different six sites were identified for sample collections on the basis of deposition of materials, accessibility to site and residential area. A complete study had been done on the physical and mechanical properties of the aggregates to find their suitability in road and concrete works. The physical properties include shape and texture, gradation, specific gravity and water absorption. The Mechanical properties include Los Angeles abrasion test, aggregate impact value and aggregate crushing value. This study helps to make a rational decision for policy makers to identify the aggregate quarries for different sustainable development activities. Sampling of sediments was done by collecting aggregates from river banks of 5 m distance from the edge of river.

Table 3.1 Sample collection location along Biring river

S. N	Spots (source)	Latitude	Longitude	Distance from origin source
1	Bhotetar	26 ° 45'32" N	88 ° 1'40" E	2 km
2	Jaypur sisne bridge	26 ° 43'24" N	88 ° 0'7" E	7 km
3	Madanpur bridge	26 ° 42' 25" N	87 ° 59'17" E	9.4 km
4	Fulmati bridge	26 ° 41'9" N	87 ° 58'51" E	11.8 km
5	DMC Causeway	26 ° 39'57" N	87 ° 57'23" E	15.3 km
6	Laxmipur highway bridge	26 ° 38'28" N	87 ° 56'13" E	19 km

Fig 3.1 Google Earth Aerial View of Sampled Site Along Biring River Basin

Fine aggregates were collected from crusher of sanischare area. Alluvial / colluvium deposit comprised of boulder, cobble, gravel and sand of predominantly gneiss, quartzite and schwas. River Basin deposited gravel and private land (borrow pit) gravel and boulders for masonry works. If the gravel were screened and selected boulders were properly crushed for the Base material, coarse aggregate from concrete and SD aggregate suitable.

3.2 Research Flowchart

The Fig. 3.2 shows the flowchart of research activity. The lab based diagnostic & descriptive along with field based empirical research design was adopted in this research work. The Process of Research starts from problem identification, defining objectives, research design, data collection, data analysis & end with conclusion with report writing.

Fig3.2: Flow Chart of Research process

3.3 Research Philosophy

Attached picture depicts the different stages in designing a research methodology by using the research onion framework.

Figure 0.3: Research Onion

The single reality is taken from ontology part and measurable are taken from epistemology part. The overall research philosophy is Positivism is in which only "factual" information obtained from observation (the senses), including measurement, is reliable. The researcher's function in this positivist studies is confined to data gathering and objective interpretation. The study outcomes in these sorts of investigations are frequently apparent and quantitative.

Abduction approach for logical reasoning was followed in which the elements of both the inductive and deductive approaches were combined. Regarding methodological choice, both qualitative as well as quantitative methods were followed. So it's a mixed method. The research strategy was experimental. As the data were collected through the different laboratory tests, this study was experimental lab-based as well as field based. The experiment was done on longitudinal time horizon. The study of a phenomena or a population over time is referred to as a longitudinal research. The data collection methods were observation method and lab based methods.

3.4 Sampling

A sample was a small portion of a larger volume or group of materials about which information was desired. Sampling was the process of obtaining samples from the large universe of population. A random sampling method was used to collect the sample from each specific prefixed location to achieve the purpose of research. Sample adequate for different tests were collected randomly at the proposed deposition. The samples were sieved and prepared at the site and then transported to the laboratory. Among the total length of river, Arjudhara Municipality section (Approx 20 Km) was considered on this study. The major basis of selection was accessibility, residential areas and deposition of materials. Though there were numerous depositions, all could not be sampled because of the inaccessibility. The major considerations that were adopted for the sampling were as follows:

1. The major deposition area was selected for sampling. It was assumed that the major deposition will be covered by the study and it can be somehow generalised for gaining the concept to other sites. The study of major deposition sites will be beneficial due to the huge quantity of material aggregate would be represented.
2. The deposition area was measured from the Google Map accessed through the internet at any time throughout the study period.
3. The length of river distance between the sampling location, coordinates and relative levels were measured through the Google Map and were tentative measurements and not so precise.
4. The accuracy of the measurement of area was dependent on the accuracy obtained through the Google Map at the period.
5. The deposition area may have changed at present and may get changed in the future due to meandering of river and river flow morphology.

3.5 Data Collection

Primary data which were collected through the lab test by the means of recording, observation, testing and measuring. Secondary source of information was collected from the different sources such as documents, data from government offices, international journals, newspapers, books, national and international research articles, different web sites and various standard codes.

3.6 General Lab Equipments for Experiment and Analysis

3.6.1 Testing of Material

Collected materials will be tested for physical as well mechanical properties as per standard testing procedures in any convenient Laboratory. Different physical test such as Gradation, Water Absorption, Specific gravity and mechanical test such as Los Angeles abrasion test, Aggregate Impact value and Aggregate Crushing value. The following test will be carried out on the labs of Infrastructure Development Office, Jhapa. During laboratory test of concrete following factors will remained unchanged throughout the study.

- Properties of cement and Sand
- Water/cement ratio
- Use of chemical and admixtures

3.6.2 Laboratory Test

1. Physical Properties

a. Sieve Analysis

This test was performed to determine the percentage of different grain sizes obtained within a source. The sieve analysis was performed to determine the distribution of the coarser, larger sized particles and the analysis was used to determine the distribution of the finer particles

Standrad Reference:

ASTMD 422- Standard Test method for particle size analysis of source.

Significance:

The distribution of different grain sizes affects the engineering properties of source. Grain size analysis provides the grain size distribution and it was required in classifying of source.

Equipment

Balance, Set of seive, cleaning brush, seive shaker, timing device

Test Procedure:

- i) Write down the weight of each seive as well as rh bottom of pan to be used in the anlaysis.
- ii) Record the weight of the given dry source sample.
- iii) Make sure that all the seive was clean and assemble them in the ascending order of sieve numbers. Carefully pour the source sample into the seive and place the cap over it.

- iv) Place the sieve stack in the mechanical/manually shaker and shake for 10 min.
- v) Remove the stack from the shaker and carefully weight and record the weight of each sieve with its retained source. In addition, remember to weight and record the weight of the bottom pan with its retained fine source.

b.Fineness Modulus Test

Fineness modulus of fine aggregates is an index number which represents the mean size of the particles in sand. It is obtained by performing sieve analysis. The cumulative percentage retained on each sieve is added and subtracted by 100 gives the value of fineness modulus. The following test procedure will be adopted to obtain fineness modulus as per("IS 2386-1 (1963)).

- a.The sieve of different sizes will be arranged in descending order.
- b.Then the aggregate sample will be poured in the top sieve and the machine will be switched on and shaking of sieve will be done at least 5 minutes.
- c.After sieving, the weight of sample retained on each sieve will be recorded and the cumulative weight will be calculated and cumulative percentage retained will be determined.
- d.After that all the cumulative percentage values will be added and will divide with 100 then the value of fineness modulus will be obtained.

c. Specific Gravity and Water Absorption Test

Specific gravity test of aggregates is conducted to measure the strength or quality of the material.

Water absorption test is conducted to determine the water holding capacity of coarse and fine aggregates. The following procedure will be conducted to determine the specific gravity and water absorption of fine and coarse aggregates as per("IS 2386-3 (1963)).

- a. About 2 kg of aggregate sample will be taken and washed to remove fines.
- b. Then the sample aggregates will be placed in the wire basket and the wire basket is then immersed in water, which is at a temperature of 22°C to 32°C.
- c. The basket, with aggregate will be kept completely immersed in water for a period of 24 ± 0.5 hour.
- d. The basket and aggregate will be weighed while suspended in water, which is at a temperature of 22°C to 32°C.

- e. The basket and aggregates will be removed from water and dried with dry absorbent cloth.
- f. The surface dried aggregates will be also weighed.
- g. The aggregate will be placed in a shallow tray and heated to 100 to 110°C in the oven for 24 ± 0.5 hours. Later, it will be cooled in an airtight container and weighed.

Apparent Specific Gravity: $W_4 / [W_4 - (W_1 - W_2)]$

Bulk Specific Gravity: $W_4 / [W_3 - (W_1 - W_2)]$

Where, W_1 = Weight of saturated aggregate and basket in water

W_2 = Weight of basket in water

W_3 = Weight of saturated aggregates in air

W_4 = Weight of oven dry aggregates in air

Water Absorption (%) = $[(W_1 - W_2) * 100] / W_2$

Where, W_1 = Weight of saturated aggregates in air

W_2 = Weight of oven dry aggregates in air

2. Mechanical Properties

a. Los Angeles Abrasion Test

This test helps to determine the abrasion value of coarse aggregate by the use of Los Angeles Machine. This test gives a measure of the aggregate resistance to abrasion and impact.

Standard reference:

Department of Road, Manuals of standard Tests

Apparatus

Los Angeles Machine, Steel Balls, WAS sieves, weight Balance

Test Procedures:

- i) Grading was selected to be used in the test such that it confirms to the grading to be used in construction, to the maximum extent possible.
- ii) 5 kg of sample was taken for grading A, B, C, D and 10 kg for grading E, F and G.
- iii) Abrasive charge was chosen as per table 2 depending on grading of aggregate.
- iv) Place the aggregates and abrasive charge on the cylinder and fix the cover.

- v) The machine is rotated at the speed of 30 to 33 revolution per minute. The number of revolution s was 500 for Grading A, B, C and D and 1000 for grading E, F and G. The machine should be balanced and driven such that there was uniform peripheral speed.
- vi) The machine was stopped after the desired number of rotations and material was discharged to the tray.
- vii) The entire stone dust was sieved on 1.7 mm WAS sieve.
- viii) The material coarser than 1.7 mm size was weighted correct to one gram.

$$\text{Abrasion Value} = (W1 - W2) / W1 * 100$$

where,

W1 = original weight of aggregate

W2 = weight of aggregate sample retained on 1.7 mm WAS Sieve

b. Aggregate Impact Test

The purpose of determining the AIV was to access its resistance to disintegration against impact loading.

Standard Reference:

Department of Road, Manual of standard tests

Appartus:

AIV appartus including measuring cylinder and temping rod. WAS sieve, Trays, weighting Balance, oven

Test procedures:

- i) Aggregates passing the whole of 12.5 mm and retained on 10 mm WAS sieve was taken.
- ii) Aggregates were filled in cylindrical measure in 3 layers by temping each layer by 25 blows. Determine the net weight of the aggregate in the measure.
- iii) The hammer was raised to height of 38 cm above the upper surface and allows falling freely on the specimen.
- iv) After subjecting to 15 blows, the crushed aggregates were sieved on WAS 2.26 mm sieve.

c. Aggregate Crushing Test

The purpose of determining the ACV was to determine the crushing strength of coarse aggregate.

Standard Reference:

Department of Road, Manual of standard tests

Appartus:

ACV appartus includinfg measuring cylinder and temping rod, WAS seive, trays, weighting Balance, oven

Test procedure:

- i) Aggregates passing the whole of 12.5mm and retained on 10 mm WAS seive was taken.
- ii) Aggregates were filled in cylinder measure in 3 layers by tamping each layer by 25 blows. Determine the net weight of aggregate in the measure.
- iii) Load was applied at uniform rate as far as possible so that total load is reached in 10 minutes (about 67kg/sec The total load is 40 tonnes

After subjecting the load for 10 minutes, the crushed aggregate was seived on WAS 2.36 mm seive.

3.Compressive Strength Test

The compressive strength of concrete will be done as per guideline given by (*IS 516 (1959): Method of Tests for Strength of Concrete*, n.d.). At least three specimen of same aggregate combination will be prepared as per IS 516 (1959) and will tested on universal compression testing machine after 7 and 28 days of curing and crushing strength of the specimen will be recorded. The test procedure will include:

- The course and fine aggregate combination will be made from aggregates collected from different six sources.
- The cement and aggregates will mix properly and after that calculated amount of water will be poured into the mix and concrete will be prepared.
- Then the prepared concrete will be placed on oiled mould of size (150x150x150 mm³) in at least three times one after another after compressed by using rammer manually (25 blows).
- After that the cube mould will store in free area lab for 24 hr.
- Then after 24 hr, the mould will removed and the concrete cube will be kept in water for 28 days.
- After 7 and 28 days, the cube will removed from water and test will be carried out on testing machine and peak load of breaking the will be recorded on record book.
- Finally, Compressive strength will be calculated by dividing peak load of breaking the cube(N) by the cross-sectional area of the cube(mm²). The mean compressive strength will

be calculated from the three data of same sample and the mean compressive strength will be used for data analysis propose.

i.e. Compressive Strength of Concrete cube =

$$\frac{\text{Peak load at which it break (N)}}{\text{Cross-sectional area of that cube(mm}^2\text{)}}$$

Mean Compressive strength =

$$\frac{\text{Sum of compressive strength of three sample}}{3}$$

3.6 Analysis of Data

Various statistical methods were used to meet the objective of the study. Data obtained as result of laboratory experiments were analysed with the statistical tool as correlation, table, charts and diagrams. The analysis was carried out using the Powerful Microsoft tool MS-Excel 2016. regression analysis was used to established relation between strength of concrete with method of least square.

CHAPTER 4 : RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter contains tabulation of all the data recorded during the test conducted, a discussion of all physical, mechanical and compressive tests, as well as outlines of the subsequent calculations needed to translate test results into the properties of the aggregates.

4.1 Physical Properties

From the lab test of aggregates from different sources were presented below.

Table 4.1 Physical Properties of Aggregates

S.N	Source of coarse Aggregate	Property	Value Obtained	DOR specification	Results
1	Bhotetar Source	Specific gravity	2.616	>2.5	Complied
		Water absorption	0.72	< 5%	Complied
		Finess Modulus	7.16	5.5-8	Complied
2	Jaypur Sisne Bridge Source	Specific gravity	2.623	>2.5	Complied
		Water absorption	0.8	< 5%	Complied
		Finess Modulus	7.32	5.5-8	Complied
3	Madanpur Bridge Source	Specific gravity	2.655	>2.5	Complied
		Water absorption	0.83	< 5%	Complied
		Finess Modulus	7.39	5.5-8	Complied
4	Fulmati bridge source	Specific gravity	2.677	>2.5	Complied
		Water absorption	0.94	< 5%	Complied
		Finess Modulus	7.42	5.5-8	Complied
5	DMC Causeway Source	Specific gravity	2.686	>2.5	Complied
		Water absorption	0.96	< 5%	Complied
		Finess Modulus	7.44	5.5-8	Complied
6	Laxmipur Highway Bridge source	Specific gravity	2.712	>2.5	Complied
		Water absorption	1.15	< 5%	Complied
		Finess Modulus	7.49	5.5-8	Complied

From the above observed value, it was found that the physical properties of the aggregates meet the criteria for the construction purpose as per DOR specification (2073). The entire source has the specific gravity greater than 2.5, Water Absorption less than 5% and fineness modulus in between 5.5-8, that is within the range of DOR specifications. The highest and the lowest value for the specific gravity and water absorption was found on Bhotetar source and Laxmipur highway bridge source respectively. A paper "An aggregate quality investigation of the meramic river gravel" (Kadri Ercin Kasapoglu 1969) also found specific gravity range (2.537-2.584), water absorption range (1.68-3.89), and fineness modulus range (6.59-7.56) of 10 different selected stations. As the specific gravity of the aggregates directly relates with the strength, the specific gravity of downstream was found to be higher than the upstream.

4.1.2 Mechanical Properties

From the Los Angles abrasion, aggregate impact value and aggregate crushing value test of the aggregates from the different source, the obtained value were presented in the table as below.

4.2 Mechanical Values of Aggregates

S.N	Location	LAA value %	AIV value %	ACV value %
1	Bhotetar source	36.4	26.7	29.4
2	Jaypur sisne bridge source	35.8	26.2	28.8
3	Madanpur bridge source	33.6	25.3	27.6
4	Fulmati bridge source	33.4	24.6	27.3
5	DMC causeway source	31.6	24.2	26.5
6	Laxmipur highway bridge source	30.9	23.7	26

From the above observed data, The LAA, AIV and ACV value was found to be highest at Bhotetar source and lowest for Laxmipur highway bridge source. The range of LAA value was (30.9-36.4) %, AIV value (23.7-36.7)%, and ACV value (26-29.4) % which meet the criteria for the construction purpose as per DOR specification (2073). A paper "An aggregate quality investigation of the meramic river gravel" (Kadri Ercin Kasapoglu

1969) also found LAA value within range (20.7-26.3) % of 10 different selected location of same Meramic river. This paper also found that LAA value goes on decreasing in lower portion of river same as Biring river Basin which indicates that the lower portion aggregate are more stronger and judged to have better strength and quality.

4.1.3 Compressive Strength

From the lab test of aggregates from the different source were presented below.

Table 4.3 Compressive Strength of Aggregates

S.N	Locations	Compressive Strength (7 days) Mpa	Compressive Strength (28 days) Mpa
1	Bhotetar source	15.43	22.69
2	Jaypur sisne bridge source	15.88	23.35
3	Madanpur bridge source	16.28	23.59
4	Fulmati bridge source	16.57	23.67
5	DMC causeway source	16.56	24
6	Laxmipur highway bridge source	17.09	24.41

From the above observed data, it was found that the cube strength of the aggregates from the Laxmipur highway bridge source have the greater strength with compressive strength of 17.09 N/mm² in 7 days and 24.41 N/mm² in 28 days. Since all the factor keeping constant, coarse aggregate were varied for different 6 sources in which the higher compressive strength was observed in Laxmipur highway bridge source and lowest in Bhotetar source.

4.2 Comparative Result Analysis of Mechanical Properties of Different Source

Table 4.4 Comparative Result Analysis (LAA)

S. N	Description of Works	Los Angeles Abrasion value (LAA)						
		As per specification	Bhotetar source	Jaypur source	Madanpur source	Fulmati source	DMC source	Laxmipur source
1	Granular sub-base							

	class I and II material							
2	Granular Sub base class III and IV material							
3	Water bound macadam for sub base	Max 45%						
4	Water bound macadam for base	Max 40%	36.4%	35.8%	33.6%	33.4%	31.6%	30.9%
5	Wet mix macadam sub base class I and II	Max 45%						
6	Wet mix macadam base class I and II	Max 40%						
7	Surface Dressing	Max 35%						
8	Dense Bituminous Macadam	Max 35%						
9	Penetration Macadam	Max 40%						
10	Bituminous Macadam	Max 40%						
	Result		complied	complied	complied	complied	complied	complied

From the above observed value, it was found that the LAA value of aggregates from all different six sources for different kinds of road construction works meet the criteria as per DOR specification (2073). A paper "An aggregate quality investigation of the ceramic

river gravel" (Kadri Ercin Kasapoglu 1969) also found LAA value within range (20.7-26.3) % of 10 different selected location of same Meramic river which also within the criteria limit for the construction works same as our findings.

Table 4.5 Comparative Result Analysis (AIV value)

S.N	Description of Works	Aggregate Impact value (AIV)						
		As per specification	Bhotetar source	Jaypur source	Madanpur source	Fulmati source	DMC source	Laxmipur source
1	Granular sub-base class I and II material	Max 40%	26.7%	26.2%	25.3%	24.6%	24.2%	23.7%
2	Granular Sub base class III and IV material	Max 45%						
3	Water bound macadam for sub base	Max 40%						
4	Water bound macadam for base	Max 30%						
5	Wet mix macadam sub base class I and II	Max 30%						
6	Wet mix macadam base class III and IV	Max 45%						
7	Surface Dressing	Max 27%						
8	Dense Bituminous	Max 27%						

	Macadam							
9	Penetration on Macadam	Max 30%						
10	Bituminous Macadam	Max 30%						
	Result		complied	complied	complied	complied	complied	complied

From the above observed value, it was found that the AIV value of aggregates from all different six sources for different kinds of road construction works meet the criteria as per DOR specification (2073). A paper "An aggregate quality investigation of the Meramic river gravel" (Kadri Ercin Kasapoglu 1969) also found AIV value within range of 10 different selected locations of same Meramic river which also within the criteria limit for the construction works same as our findings.

Table 4.6 Comparative Result Analysis (ACV value)

S. N	Description of Works	Aggregate crushing value (ACV)						
		As per specification	Bhotetar source	Jaypur source	Madanpur source	Fulmati source	DMC source	Laxmi pur source
1	Granular sub-base class I and II material	Max 40%						
2	Granular Sub base class III and IV material	Max 45%						
3	Water bound macadam for sub base	Max 40%						
4	Water bound macadam for base	Max 30%						
5	Wet mix	Max 30%	26.7%	26.2%	25.3%	24.6%	24.2%	23.7%

	macadam sub base class I and II							
6	Wet mix macadam base class III and IV	Max 45%						
7	Surface Dressing	Max 27%						
8	Dense Bituminous Macadam	Max 27%						
9	Penetration Macadam	Max 30%						
10	Bituminous Macadam	Max 30%						
	Result		complied	complied	complied	complied	Complied	Complied

From the above observed value, it was found that the ACV value of aggregates from all different six source for different kinds of road construction works meet the criteria as per DOR specification (2073). A paper "An aggregate quality investigation of the meramic river gravel" (Kadri Ercin Kasapoglu 1969) also found ACV value within range of 10 different selected location of same Meramic river which also within the criteria limit for the construction works same as our findings.

figure 4.1: Graphical representation of LAA and Distance (KM)

figure 4.2: Graphical representation of AIV and Distance (KM)

Figure 4.3: Graphical representation of ACV value and Distance (KM)

Figure 4.3: Graphical representation of compressive strength (28 days) and Distance (KM)

From the graph it was found that the abrasion, impact and crushing value of the aggregates goes on decreasing downwards due to wear and tear action of the river. The value compressive strength of cube goes on increasing using the aggregates of lower portion of Biring river basin. As the highest value of LAA, AIV and ACV was found on the Bhotetar source whereas the lowest value was obtained for Laxmipur highway bridge source. The lower portion of Biring river Basin is found to have relatively better strength and quality of aggregate. A paper "An aggregate quality investigation of the meramic river gravel" (Kadri Ercin Kasapoglu 1969) also studied different 10 station of same meramic river and found that the lower portion of meramic river have relatively better quality of aggregate for construction same as our study.

Different linear equation developed where x = distance from the origin source
for abrasion value

$$y = -0.352x + 37.41 \dots\dots\dots (i)$$

for impact value

$$y = -0.189x + 27.15 \dots\dots\dots (ii)$$

for crushing value

$$y = -0.212x + 29.88 \dots\dots\dots (iii)$$

for 28 days compressive strength

$$y = 0.095x + 22.58 \dots\dots\dots (iv)$$

4.3 Economic Contribution of Biring river aggregate Extraction

In Fiscal year 2077/78, Arjundhara Municipality had invitation of Bid to sell the aggregates of Biring River in two Package according to the approved IEE report.

S.N	Contract No.	Abstract Amount aggregate (Cum) according to Approved IEE	Minimum Bid Amount (without VAT)
1	AM/IR/04/077/78 (Package 1)	54000 cum	1,02,18,395/- (One crore two lakhs eighteen Thousand three hundred ninty five only.)
2	AM/IR/05/077/78 (Package 2)	39050 cum	67,58,496.41/- (Sixty seven Lakhs fifty eight thousand four hundred ninty six and forty one paisa only)

Total:	93050 cum	1,69,76,891.41/- (One crore sixty nine lakhs seventy six thousand, eight hundred ninty one and forty one paisa only)
Forecasted Internal source of Income for Fiscal Year 2077/78		5,50,00,000/- (Five crore fifty lakhs only)
Weightage of the Income generated from extraction of Biring River to the total predicted Internal source of Income	$\frac{(16976891.41/55000000)*10}{0\%}$ $= 30.86\%$	

For Arjunthara Municipality, the major portion of the internal source of Income was found to be from income generated from extraction of the river aggregates of Biring River basin. The weightage of Income generated to total predicted Internal source of Income of Arjunthara Municipality was about 30.86%.

CHAPTER-5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study was done to find out the variation of aggregates strength along the biring river basin. For this purpose, samples were collected from different sources of six different locations. Physical and mechanical tests were outlined by Department of Roads. The physical tests were seive analysis, specific gravity and water absorption and Mechanical test consists of LAA test, ACV test and AIV test.

5.1 Key Findings

1. The specific gravity of the aggregates were found to be varied in the range of 2.616 to 2.712 The specific gravity of the aggregates was found to be satisfactory.
2. The water absorption value for different sources was found to be varied from 0.72 % to 1.15% which is satisfactory.
3. The average percent of LAA value for the aggregate samples is 33.62% which is satisfactory according to DOR specification for construction aggregates. Aggregate sample from Bhotetar source had the most abrasion loss(36.40%) but it was still below the maximum allowable loss specified by DOR, which is 45% by weight for coarse aggregates. Each of the sample tested had an LAA value below this limit. Sample of Laxmipur highway bridge source had the lowest value (30.9%) of all those tested. The variation of the LAA value was from 30.9% to 36.40% The general equation of $y = -0.3526x + 37.41$ was obtained where $x =$ distance from origin source.
4. The average value of AIV for the aggregates sample is 25.12% which is satisfactory according to DOR specifications for construction aggregates. Aggregate of Bhotetar source has the most impact loss (26.70%), but it was still below the the maximum allowable loss specified by DOR, which is 30% by weight for the coarse aggregates. Each of the samples tested had AIV value below this limit. Sample of Laxmipur highway bridge source had the lowest AIV value (23.70%) of all those tested. The variation of the AIV was from 23.70% to 26.70%.The general equation of $y = -0.189x + 27.15$ was obtained, where $x =$ distance from origin source.
5. The average value of ACV for the aggregate samples is 27.60% which is satisfactory according to the DOR specification for construction aggregates.

Aggregates sample from the Bhotetar had the most crushing loss (29.40%) but still below the maximum allowable loss specified by DOR, which is 30% by weight for coarse aggregates. Each of the samples tested had the ACV below this limit. Sample of the Laxmipur highway bridge source had the lowest ACV (26.0%) of those all tested. the variation of ACV value was from 26% to 29.4%. The general equation of $y = - 0.212x + 29.88$ was obtained, where $x =$ distance from origin source.

6. The average percent of the compressive strength of the cube casted from the different sample was found to be 23.62 N/mm² for 28 days. The highest compressive strength is from the Laxmipur highway bridge source (24.41 N/mm²) with the lowest value of Bhotetar of 22.69 N/mm².
7. The weightage of source of Income generated by extraction of the aggregates of the Biring river basin to total internal source of Income of Arjundhara Municipality was about 30.86%.

5.2 Conclusion

The results of these various studies lead to the following conclusions on the qualitative evaluation of the Biring river aggregates:

1. The physical and mechanical properties of aggregates of Biring river Basin was found to be satisfactory in all six selected section of Biring river Basin. The physical and mechanical strength of aggregates goes on increasing along going from upstream to downstream of Biring river. The lower portion of river have relatively better quality of aggregate.
2. The compressive strength of the cubes casted from all six selected section of Biring river basin was satisfactory and with the standard required.. The compressive strength of cube prepared by aggregate of lower portion of river have relatively greater compressive strength than upper portion.
3. The source of Income generated by extraction of the aggregates of the Biring river basin has significant contribution in the total internal source of Income of Arjundhara Municipality.

5.3 Recommendations

All the results obtained from the laboratory testing of the samples were compared with the properties requirements for different types of roads and concrete works as per Standard Specifications for Road and Bridge works published and used by ministry of Physical Infrastructure and Transport, Department of Roads. The test results were obtained through the Laboratory test from the collected samples from different six locations along the Biring river Basin. It was found that the aggregate from all the source complied the minimum required value regarding the strength for the construction work under the scope of this study. Hence it is recommended to use the aggregate material from Biring river from the study area for the construction of any construction works. The strength of aggregate increases toward downstream of river so when high strength of concrete is required aggregate from downstream source can be used.

The financial status of any local government will be strong if only its internal source of Income is high. This source can be used in different development works initiated by the local government for the betterment of the people and the society. If extraction of aggregates from Biring river basin can be done scientifically then Internal source of Income can be increased.

5.4 Recommendation for further study

For a better evaluation of the aggregate materials from the Biring River, more extensive studies consisting of the following procedures are recommended for the further study.

1. Establishment of relationship between physical and mechanical properties of the aggregates along the Biring river basin.
2. Chemical properties of the aggregates can be considered for the further study of the relationship.
3. Aggregate property of the tributary rivers can be considered to study the effect of the mixed aggregates.
4. Optimization study for the strength and cost can be established among the different source along the Biring river basins.
5. Quantity survey for the aggregates materials for accessing appropriate quantity that can be abstracted from different depositions along the bank of Biring river basin.

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ANNEX

Annex-1

Seive Analysis Report

Bhotetar Source						
Seive size in mm	Retained wt (gm)	Cum Ret wt (gm)	% retained by wt	% passing by wt	specification Limit	
					Min	Max
63	0	0	0.00	100.00	100.0	100.0
40	298	298	14.90	85.10	70.0	100.0
20	336	634	31.70	68.30	50.0	85.0
10	403	1037	51.85	48.15	40.0	75.0
4.75	313	1350	67.50	32.50	30.0	60.0
2.36	180	1530	76.50	23.50	20.0	45.0
1.18	160	1690	84.50	15.50	15.0	35.0
0.08	250	1940	97.00	3.00	4.0	15.0
Pan	60	2000	100.00	0.00		
Total Wt in gm	2000.00					
Median size grain	19.499					
Jaypur Sisne bridge source						
Seive size in mm	Retained wt (gm)	Cum Ret wt (gm)	% retained by wt	% passing by wt	specification Limit	
					Min	Max
63	0	0	0.00	100.00	100.0	100.0
40	270	270	13.50	86.50	70.0	100.0
20	329	599	29.95	70.05	50.0	85.0
10	473	1072	53.60	46.40	40.0	75.0
4.75	313	1385	69.25	30.75	30.0	60.0
2.36	205	1590	79.50	20.50	20.0	45.0
1.18	150	1740	87.00	13.00	15.0	35.0
0.08	170	1910	95.50	4.50	4.0	15.0
Pan	90	2000	100.00	0.00		

Total Wt in gm	2000.00					
Median size grain	19.781					
Madanpur source						
Seive size in mm	Retained wt (gm)	Cum Ret wt (gm)	% retained by wt	% passing by wt	specification Limit	
					Min	Max
63	0	0	0.00	100.00	100.0	100.0
40	198	198	9.90	90.10	70.0	100.0
20	336	534	26.70	73.30	50.0	85.0
10	403	937	46.85	53.15	40.0	75.0
4.75	313	1250	62.50	37.50	30.0	60.0
2.36	280	1530	76.50	23.50	20.0	45.0
1.18	160	1690	84.50	15.50	15.0	35.0
0.08	250	1940	97.00	3.00	4.0	15.0
Pan	60	2000	100.00	0.00		
Total Wt in gm	2000.00					
Median size grain	17.956					
Fulmati bridge source						
Seive size in mm	Retained wt (gm)	Cum Ret wt (gm)	% retained by wt	% passing by wt	specification Limit	
					Min	Max
63	0	0	0.00	100.00	100.0	100.0
40	188	188	8.55	91.45	70.0	100.0
20	336	524	23.82	76.18	50.0	85.0
10	503	1027	46.68	53.32	40.0	75.0
4.75	423	1450	65.91	34.09	30.0	60.0
2.36	280	1730	78.64	21.36	20.0	45.0
1.18	160	1890	85.91	14.09	15.0	35.0
0.08	250	2140	97.27	2.73	4.0	15.0
Pan	60	2200	100.00	0.00		
Total Wt in gm	2200.00					

Median size grain		17.513				
DMC causeway source						
Seive size in mm	Retained wt (gm)	Cum Ret wt (gm)	% retained by wt	% passing by wt	specification Limit	
					Min	Max
63	0	0	0.00	100.00	100.0	100.0
40	298	298	14.90	85.10	70.0	100.0
20	236	534	26.70	73.30	50.0	85.0
10	403	937	46.85	53.15	40.0	75.0
4.75	313	1250	62.50	37.50	30.0	60.0
2.36	280	1530	76.50	23.50	20.0	45.0
1.18	160	1690	84.50	15.50	15.0	35.0
0.08	250	1940	97.00	3.00	4.0	15.0
Pan	60	2000	100.00	0.00		
Total Wt in gm	2000.00					
Median size grain		18.332				
Laxmipur highway bridge source						
Seive size in mm	Retained wt (gm)	Cum Ret wt (gm)	% retained by wt	% passing by wt	specification Limit	
					Min	Max
63	0	0	0.00	100.00	100.0	100.0
40	298	298	14.90	85.10	70.0	100.0
20	304	602	30.10	69.90	50.0	85.0
10	405	1007	50.35	49.65	40.0	75.0
4.75	316	1323	66.15	33.85	30.0	60.0
2.36	210	1533	76.65	23.35	20.0	45.0
1.18	157	1690	84.50	15.50	15.0	35.0
0.08	250	1940	97.00	3.00	4.0	15.0
Pan	60	2000	100.00	0.00		
Total Wt in gm	2000.00					
Median size grain		18.552				

Annex -2

SPECIFIC GRAVITY AND WATER ABSORPTION						
Bhotetar source						
S. N	Description		Unit	1	2	Average
1	Wt. of Saturated Aggregate and Basket in Water, W1	W_1	gms	2810	2890	
2	Wt. of Basket in Water, W2	W_2	gms	590	590	
3	Wt. of Saturated Surface Dry Aggregate in Air, W3	W_3	gms	3645	3725	
4	Wt. of Oven Dried Aggregate in Air, W4	W_4	gms	3622	3695	
5	Wt. of Saturated Aggregate in Water, W5	W_1-W_2	gms	2220	2300	
6	Bulk Specific Gravity (SSD) =	$W_3/(W_3-(W_1-W_2))$	gms	2.558	2.614	
7	Bulk Specific Gravity (Dry) =	$W_4/(W_3-(W_1-W_2))$		2.542	2.593	
8	Apparent Specific Gravity =	$W_4/(W_4-W_5)$	gms	2.583	2.649	2.616
9	Water Absorption (%) =	$(W_3-W_4)/W_4$	%	0.635	0.812	0.72

Jaypur sisne bridge source						
S.N	Description		Unit	1	2	Average
1	Wt. of Saturated Aggregate and Basket in Water, W1	W_1	gms	2840	2900	
2	Wt. of Basket in Water, W2	W_2	gms	590	590	
3	Wt. of Saturated Surface Dry Aggregate in Air, W3	W_3	gms	3652	3725	
4	Wt. of Oven Dried Aggregate in Air, W4	W_4	gms	3620	3696	

5	Wt. of Saturated Aggregate in Water, W ₅	$W_1 - W_2$	gms	2250	2310	
6	Bulk Specific Gravity (SSD) =	$W_3 / (W_3 - (W_1 - W_2))$	gms	2.605	2.633	
7	Bulk Specific Gravity (Dry) =	$W_4 / (W_3 - (W_1 - W_2))$	gms	2.582	2.612	
8	Apparent Specific Gravity =	$W_4 / (W_4 - W_5)$	gms	2.642	2.667	2.655
9	Water Absorption (%) =	$(W_3 - W_4) / W_4$	%	0.884	0.785	0.83

Madanpur bridge source						
S. N	Description		Unit	1	2	Average
1	Wt. of Saturated Aggregate and Basket in Water, W ₁	W_1	gms	2840	2900	
2	Wt. of Basket in Water, W ₂	W_2	gms	590	590	
3	Wt. of Saturated Surface Dry Aggregate in Air, W ₃	W_3	gms	3652	3725	
4	Wt. of Oven Dried Aggregate in Air, W ₄	W_4	gms	3620	3696	
5	Wt. of Saturated Aggregate in Water, W ₅	$W_1 - W_2$	gms	2250	2310	
6	Bulk Specific Gravity (SSD) =	$W_3 / (W_3 - (W_1 - W_2))$	gms	2.605	2.633	
7	Bulk Specific Gravity (Dry) =	$W_4 / (W_3 - (W_1 - W_2))$	gms	2.582	2.612	
8	Apparent Specific Gravity =	$W_4 / (W_4 - W_5)$	gms	2.642	2.667	2.655
9	Water Absorption (%) =	$(W_3 - W_4) / W_4$	%	0.884	0.785	0.83

Fulmati bridge source						
S. N	Description		Unit	1	2	Average
1	Wt. of Saturated Aggregate and Basket in Water, W ₁	W_1	gms	2853	2910	
2	Wt. of Basket in Water, W ₂	W_2	gms	590	590	

3	Wt. of Saturated Surface Dry Aggregate in Air, W3	W_3	gms	3655	3730	
4	Wt. of Oven Dried Aggregate in Air, W4	W_4	gms	3620	3696	
5	Wt. of Saturated Aggregate in Water, W5	W_1-W_2	gms	2263	2320	
6	Bulk Specific Gravity (SSD) =	$W_3/(W_3-(W_1-W_2))$	gms	2.626	2.645	
7	Bulk Specific Gravity (Dry) =	$W_4/(W_3-(W_1-W_2))$	gms	2.601	2.621	
8	Apparent Specific Gravity =	$W_4/(W_4-W_5)$	gms	2.668	2.686	2.677
9	Water Absorption (%) =	$(W_3-W_4)/W_4$	%	0.967	0.920	0.94

DMC Causeway source						
S. N	Description		Unit	1	2	Average
1	Wt. of Saturated Aggregate and Basket in Water, W1	W_1	Gms	2855	2915	
2	Wt. of Basket in Water, W2	W_2	Gms	590	590	
3	Wt. of Saturated Surface Dry Aggregate in Air, W3	W_3	Gms	3653	3730	
4	Wt. of Oven Dried Aggregate in Air, W4	W_4	Gms	3620	3693	
5	Wt. of Saturated Aggregate in Water, W5	W_1-W_2	Gms	2265	2325	
6	Bulk Specific Gravity (SSD) =	$W_3/(W_3-(W_1-W_2))$	Gms	2.632	2.655	
7	Bulk Specific Gravity (Dry) =	$W_4/(W_3-(W_1-W_2))$	Gms	2.608	2.628	
8	Apparent Specific Gravity =	$W_4/(W_4-W_5)$	Gms	2.672	2.700	2.686
9	Water Absorption (%) =	$(W_3-W_4)/W_4$	%	0.912	1.002	0.96

Laxmipur highway Bridge source						
S.N	Description		Unit	1	2	Average
1	Wt. of Saturated Aggregate and Basket in Water, W ₁	W ₁	Gms	2863	2935	
2	Wt. of Basket in Water, W ₂	W ₂	Gms	590	590	
3	Wt. of Saturated Surface Dry Aggregate in Air, W ₃	W ₃	Gms	3664	3732	
4	Wt. of Oven Dried Aggregate in Air, W ₄	W ₄	Gms	3623	3689	
5	Wt. of Saturated Aggregate in Water, W ₅	W ₁ -W ₂	Gms	2273	2345	
6	Bulk Specific Gravity (SSD) =	$W_3/(W_3-(W_1-W_2))$	Gms	2.634	2.691	
7	Bulk Specific Gravity (Dry) =	$W_4/(W_3-(W_1-W_2))$	Gms	2.605	2.660	
8	Apparent Specific Gravity =	$W_4/(W_4-W_5)$	Gms	2.684	2.745	2.714
9	Water Absorption (%) =	$(W_3-W_4)/W_4$	%	1.132	1.166	1.15

ANNEX-3

LOS ANGELES ABRASION TEST

Sample Preparation					
S.No	Sieve size (mm)	Units	1	2	
1	20-12.5	Gm	2500±50		
2	12.5-10	Gm	2500±50		
Bhotetar Source					
Grading	Units		B		Specified
Number of Revolutions			500		
Total Weight of Test Sample	(gm)		5000	5000	

Weight of Test Sample Retained on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)		3210	3150	
Weight of Test Sample passed on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)		1790	1850	
Percent Loss	%		35.8	37.0	Max ≤ 40%
Average Loss Abrasion Percent Value	%	36.4			
Jaypur sisne bridge source					
Grading	Units		B		Specified
Number of Revolutions			500		
Total Weight of Test Sample	(gm)		5000	5000	
Weight of Test Sample Retained on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)		3200	3220	
Weight of Test Sample passed on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)		1800	1780	
Percent Loss	%		36.0	35.6	Max ≤ 40%
Average Loss Abrasion Percent Value	%	35.8			
Madanpur bridge source					
Grading	Units		B		Specified
Number of Revolutions			500		
Total Weight of Test Sample	(gm)		5000	5000	
Weight of Test Sample Retained on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)		3310	3330	
Weight of Test Sample passed on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)		1690	1670	

Percent Loss	%		33.8	33.4	Max ≤ 40%
Average Loss Abrasion Percent Value	%		33.6		
Fulmati bridge source					
Grading	Units		B		Specified
Number of Revolutions			500		
Total Weight of Test Sample	(gm)		5000	5000	
Weight of Test Sample Retained on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)		3320	3340	
Weight of Test Sample passed on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)		1680	1660	
Percent Loss	%		33.6	33.2	Max ≤ 40%
Average Loss Abrasion Percent Value	%		33.4		
DMC causeway source					
Grading	Units		B		Specified
Number of Revolutions			500		
Total Weight of Test Sample	(gm)		5000	5000	
Weight of Test Sample Retained on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)		3420	3425	
Weight of Test Sample passed on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)		1580	1575	
Percent Loss	%		31.6	31.5	Max ≤ 40%
Average Loss Abrasion Percent Value	%		31.6		
Laxmipur highway bridge source					
Grading	Units		B		Specified

Number of Revolutions		500		
Total Weight of Test Sample	(gm)	5000	5000	
Weight of Test Sample Retained on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)	3450	3465	
Weight of Test Sample passed on No.1.7 Sieve	(gm)	1550	1535	
Percent Loss	%	31.0	30.7	Max ≤ 40%
Average Loss Abrasion Percent Value	%	30.9		

ANNEX- 4

Aggregate Impact Value Test (AIV)

		Bhotetar Source			
Sample Preparation : Aggregate passing 12.5 mm sieve and Retained on 10 mm sieve.					
Test No	Description	Units	1	2	Remarks
A1	Weight of cylindrical measure + sample, A1	Gm	965.0	960.0	
A2	Weight of Cylindrical Measure A2	Gm	591.5	591.5	
A	Weight of Sample =(A1-A2)	Gm	373.5	368.5	
Test Procedure					
Trail No.	Description	Units	Test Number		Remarks
			1	2	
B	Weight of aggregate retained 2.36mm sieve after the test	Gm	273.0	271.0	
C	Weight of aggregate passing on 2.36 mm sieve after the test	Gm	100.5	97.5	
D	Total weight =B+C	Gm	373.5	368.5	

E	Aggregate Impact Value = percent fines = (C/A)*100	%	26.9	26.5	
F	Average Aggregate Impact Value	%	26.7		
G	Specifications	%	≤ 30		
		Jaypur sisne bridge source			
Test No	Description	Units	1	2	Remarks
A1	Weight of cylindrical measure + sample, A1	Gm	964.0	958.0	
A2	Weight of Cylindrical Measure A2	Gm	591.5	591.5	
A	Weight of Sample =(A1-A2)	Gm	372.5	366.5	
Test Procedure					
Trail No.	Description	Units	Test Number		Remarks
			1	2	
B	Weight of aggregate retained 2.36mm sieve after the test	Gm	272.0	273.0	
C	Weight of aggregate passing on 2.36 mm sieve after the test	Gm	100.5	93.5	
D	Total weight =B+C	Gm	372.5	366.5	
E	Aggregate Impact Value = percent fines = (C/A)*100	%	27.0	25.5	
F	Average Aggregate Impact Value	%	26.2		
G	Specifications	%	≤ 30		
		Madanpur bridge source			
Test No	Description	Units	1	2	Remarks
A1	Weight of cylindrical measure + sample, A1	Gm	958.0	960.0	
A2	Weight of Cylindrical Measure A2	Gm	591.5	591.5	
A	Weight of Sample =(A1-A2)	Gm	366.5	368.5	
Test Procedure					
Trail No.	Description	Units	Test Number		Remarks
			1	2	
B	Weight of aggregate retained 2.36mm sieve	Gm	274.0	275.0	

	after the test				
C	Weight of aggregate passing on 2.36 mm sieve after the test	Gm	92.5	93.5	
D	Total weight =B+C	Gm	366.5	368.5	
E	Aggregate Impact Value = percent fines = (C/A)*100	%	25.2	25.4	
F	Average Aggregate Impact Value	%	25.3		
G	Specifications	%	≤ 30		
Fulmati bridge source					
Test No	Description	Units	1	2	Remarks
A1	Weight of cylindrical measure + sample, A1	Gm	957.0	955.0	
A2	Weight of Cylindrical Measure A2	Gm	591.5	591.5	
A	Weight of Sample =(A1-A2)	Gm	365.5	363.5	
Test Procedure					
Trail No.	Description	Units	Test Number		Remarks
			1	2	
B	Weight of aggregate retained 2.36mm sieve after the test	Gm	274.0	276.0	
C	Weight of aggregate passing on 2.36 mm sieve after the test	Gm	91.5	87.5	
D	Total weight =B+C	Gm	365.5	363.5	
E	Aggregate Impact Value = percent fines = (C/A)*100	%	25.0	24.1	
F	Average Aggregate Impact Value	%	24.6		
G	Specifications	%	≤ 30		
DMC causeway source					
Test No	Description	Units	1	2	Remarks
A1	Weight of cylindrical measure + sample, A1	Gm	962.0	958.0	
A2	Weight of Cylindrical Measure A2	Gm	591.5	591.5	
A	Weight of Sample =(A1-A2)	Gm	370.5	366.5	
Test Procedure					

Trail No.	Description	Units	Test Number		Remarks
			1	2	
B	Weight of aggregate retained 2.36mm sieve after the test	Gm	280.0	279.0	
C	Weight of aggregate passing on 2.36 mm sieve after the test	Gm	90.5	87.5	
D	Total weight =B+C	Gm	370.5	366.5	
E	Aggregate Impact Value = percent fines = (C/A)*100	%	24.4	23.9	
F	Average Aggregate Impact Value	%	24.2		
G	Specifications	%	≤ 30		
Laxmipur highway bridge source					
Test No	Description	Units	1	2	Remarks
A1	Weight of cylindrical measure + sample, A1	Gm	964.0	958.0	
A2	Weight of Cylindrical Measure A2	Gm	591.5	591.5	
A	Weight of Sample =(A1-A2)	Gm	372.5	366.5	
Test Procedure					
Trail No.	Description	Units	Test Number		Remarks
			1	2	
B	Weight of aggregate retained 2.36mm sieve after the test	Gm	281.0	283.0	
C	Weight of aggregate passing on 2.36 mm sieve after the test	Gm	91.5	83.5	
D	Total weight =B+C	Gm	372.5	366.5	
E	Aggregate Impact Value = percent fines = (C/A)*100	%	24.6	22.8	
F	Average Aggregate Impact Value	%	23.7		
G	Specifications	%	≤ 30		
*Note: If "D" differs by more than 1gm to "A", repeat the test					

Annex-5

Aggregate Crushing Value Test (ACV)

		Bhotetar Source			
Sample Preparation		: Aggregate passing 12.5 mm sieve and Retained on 10 mm sieve.			
Test Procedure					
Trail No.	Description	Units	Test Number		Remarks
			1	2	
C	Wt. of container (gm)	gm	450.0	450.0	
A	Wt. of surface dry specimen + container (gm)	gm	3392.0	3387.0	
B	Wt. of fines passing 2.36 mm IS Seive + container (gm)	gm	1310.0	1320.0	
E	Crushing strength of coarse Aggregates $((B-C)/(A-C))*100$	%	29.2	29.6	
F	Average AggregateCrushing Value	%	29.4		
G	specifications	%	≤ 30		
		Jaypur sisne bridge source			
Test Procedure					
Trail No.	Description	Units	Test Number		Remarks
			1	2	
C	Wt. of container (gm)	gm	450.0	450.0	
A	Wt. of surface dry specimen + container (gm)	gm	3410.0	3420.0	
B	Wt. of fines passing 2.36 mm IS Seive + container (gm)	gm	1295.0	1310.0	
E	Crushing strength of coarse Aggregates $((B-C)/(A-C))*100$	%	28.5	29.0	
F	Average AggregateCrushing Value	%	28.8		
G	specifications	%	≤ 30		

		Madanpur bridge source			
Test Procedure					
Trail No.	Description	Units	Test Number		Remarks
			1	2	
C	Wt. of container (gm)	gm	450.0	450.0	
A	Wt. of surface dry specimen + container (gm)	gm	3420.0	3425.0	
B	Wt. of fines passing 2.36 mm IS Sieve + container (gm)	gm	1270.0	1270.0	
E	Crushing strength of coarse Aggregates $((B-C)/(A-C))*100$	%	27.6	27.6	
F	Average AggregateCrushing Value	%	27.6		
G	specifications	%	≤ 30		
		Fulmati bridge source			
Test Procedure					
Trail No.	Description	Units	Test Number		Remarks
			1	2	
C	Wt. of container (gm)	gm	450.0	450.0	
A	Wt. of surface dry specimen + container (gm)	gm	3430.0	3435.0	
B	Wt. of fines passing 2.36 mm IS Sieve + container (gm)	gm	1270.0	1260.0	
E	Crushing strength of coarse Aggregates $((B-C)/(A-C))*100$	%	27.5	27.1	
F	Average AggregateCrushing Value	%	27.3		
G	specifications	%	≤ 30		
		DMC causeway source			
Test Procedure					
Trail No.	Description	Units	Test Number		Remarks
			1	2	
C	Wt. of container (gm)	gm	450.0	450.0	
A	Wt. of surface dry specimen + container (gm)	gm	3450.0	3455.0	

B	Wt. of fines passing 2.36 mm IS Sieve + container (gm)	gm	1250.0	1240.0	
E	Crushing strength of coarse Aggregates $((B-C)/(A-C))*100$	%	26.7	26.3	
F	Average AggregateCrushing Value	%	26.5		
G	specifications	%	≤ 30		
		Laxmipur highway bridge source			
Test Procedure					
Trail No.	Description	Units	Test Number		Remarks
			1	2	
C	Wt. of container (gm)	gm	450.0	450.0	
A	Wt. of surface dry specimen + container (gm)	gm	3455.0	3460.0	
B	Wt. of fines passing 2.36 mm IS Sieve + container (gm)	gm	1235.0	1230.0	
E	Crushing strength of coarse Aggregates $((B-C)/(A-C))*100$	%	26.1	25.9	
F	Average AggregateCrushing Value	%	26.0		
G	specifications	%	≤ 30		

Annex - 5

Compressive Strength Tested Value

Concrete Grade: M20/20

Bhotetar source				
S.N	Sample No.	1	2	3
1	Age	7 days	7 days	7 days
2	Dimension (L*B*H) (cm)	15*15*15	15*15*15	15*15*15
3	Surface Area (cm ²)	225	225	225
4	Volume (cm ³)	3375	3375	3375

5	Breaking Load (kN)	345	342.000	355.000
6	Breaking strength (N/mm ²)	15.33	15.20	15.78
7	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	15.437		
Jaypur Sisne bridge source				
S.N	Sample No.	1	2	3
1	Age	7 days	7 days	7 days
2	Dimension (L*B*H) (cm)	15*15*15	15*15*15	15*15*15
3	Surface Area (cm ²)	225	225	225
4	Volume (cm ³)	3375	3375	3375
5	Breaking Load (kN)	358	344	370
6	Breaking strength (N/mm ²)	15.91	15.29	16.44
7	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	15.88		
Madanpur bridge source				
S.N	Sample No.	1	2	3
1	Age	7 days	7 days	7 days
2	Dimension (L*B*H) (cm)	15*15*15	15*15*15	15*15*15
3	Surface Area (cm ²)	225	225	225
4	Volume (cm ³)	3375	3375	3375
5	Breaking Load (kN)	366	360	373
6	Breaking strength (N/mm ²)	16.27	16.00	16.58
7	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	16.28		
Fulmati bridge source				
S.N	Sample No.	1	2	3
1	Age	7 days	7 days	7 days
2	Dimension (L*B*H) (cm)	15*15*15	15*15*15	15*15*15
3	Surface Area (cm ²)	225	225	225
4	Volume (cm ³)	3375	3375	3375
5	Breaking Load (kN)	378	366	375

6	Breaking strength (N/mm ²)	16.80	16.27	16.67
7	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	16.58		
DMC causeway source				
S.N	Sample No.	1	2	3
1	Age	7 days	7 days	7 days
2	Dimension (L*B*H) (cm)	15*15*15	15*15*15	15*15*15
3	Surface Area (cm ²)	225	225	225
4	Volume (cm ³)	3375	3375	3375
5	Breaking Load (kN)	380	366	372
6	Breaking strength (N/mm ²)	16.89	16.27	16.53
7	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	16.56		
Laxmipur highway source				

S.N	Sample No.	1	2	3
1	Age	7 days	7 days	7 days
2	Dimension (L*B*H) (cm)	15*15*15	15*15*15	15*15*15
3	Surface Area (cm ²)	225	225	225
4	Volume (cm ³)	3375	3375	3375
5	Breaking Load (kN)	380	390	383
6	Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	16.89	17.33	17.02
7	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	17.08		

Annex - 6

Compressive Strength Tested Value

Concrete Grade: M20/20

Bhotetar source				
S.N	Sample No.	1	2	3
1	Age	28 days	28 days	28 days
2	Dimension (L*B*H) (cm)	15*15*15	15*15*15	15*15*15 5

3	Surface Area (cm ²)	225	225	225
4	Volume (cm ³)	3375	3375	3375
5	Breaking Strength (KN)	507	502	522
6	Breaking strength (N/mm ²)	22.53	22.31	23.20
7	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	22.681		
Jaypur Sisne bridge source				
S.N	Sample No.	1	2	3
1	Age	28 days	28 days	28 days
2	Dimension (L*B*H) (cm)	15*15*15	15*15*15	15*15*15
3	Surface Area (cm ²)	225	225	225
4	Volume (cm ³)	3375	3375	3375
5	Breaking Strength (KN)	526	509	541
6	Breaking strength (N/mm ²)	23.38	22.62	24.04
7	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	23.35		
Madanpur bridge source				
S.N	Sample No.	1	2	3
1	Age	28 days	28 days	28 days
2	Dimension (L*B*H) (cm)	15*15*15	15*15*15	15*15*15
3	Surface Area (cm ²)	225	225	225
4	Volume (cm ³)	3375	3375	3375
5	Breaking Strength (KN)	530	522	540
6	Breaking strength (N/mm ²)	23.56	23.20	24.00
7	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	23.59		
Fulmati bridge source				
S.N	Sample No.	1	2	3
1	Age	28 days	28 days	28 days
2	Dimension (L*B*H) (cm)	15*15*15	15*15*15	15*15*15

3	Surface Area (cm ²)	225	225	225
4	Volume (cm ³)	3375	3375	3375
5	Breaking Load (kN)	7.23	7.122	7.282
6	Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	539	522	537
7	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	23.96	23.20	23.87
9	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	23.67		
DMC causeway source				
S.N	Sample No.	1	2	3
1	Age	28 days	28 days	28 days
2	Dimension (L*B*H) (cm)	15*15*15	15*15*15	15*15*15
3	Surface Area (cm ²)	225	225	225
4	Volume (cm ³)	3375	3375	3375
5	Breaking Load (kN)	7.17	7.233	7.232
6	Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	551	530	539
7	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	24.49	23.56	23.96
9	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	24.00		
Laxmipur highway bridge source				
S.N	Sample No.	1	2	3
1	Age	28 days	28 days	28 days
2	Dimension (L*B*H) (cm)	15*15*15	15*15*15	15*15*15
3	Surface Area (cm ²)	225	225	225
4	Volume (cm ³)	3375	3375	3375
5	Breaking Load (kN)	7.222	7.129	7.311
6	Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	543	557	548
7	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	24.13	24.76	24.36
9	Avg. Breaking Strength (N/mm ²)	24.41		

ANNEX-7

PHOTOGRAPHS OF LABORATORY TEST

P1: SAMPLE AFTER SEIVE ANALYSIS

P2: COLLECTION OF SAMPLE

P3: TESTING OF COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF CUBE